

Information systems, modern information technologies and systems in the education, education and development of an individual.

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Annotation

Pedagogical software tools are didactic tools designed to partially or completely automate the educational process using computer technology. They are considered one of the promising forms of improving the effectiveness of the educational process and are used as a teaching tool of modern technologies. Pedagogical software tools include: a software product (a set of programs), technical and methodological support, additional auxiliary tools aimed at achieving specific didactic goals in educational science.

Base words: education, information, communication, method, application, automation, didactics, tool, complex, animation.

The use of information and communication technologies in the educational process is a time requirement. Without the use of modern methods of teaching and information and communication technologies, the teacher will not be able to achieve effective results in his professional activities. But in this it is important to correctly choose the goals and content, methods and means of education and organizational forms.

With the increasing flow of information and the complication of educational methods, it is increasingly difficult to organize education mainly in the traditional way. The means of information and communication technology are of particular importance in the educational process and provide an incredibly wide range of opportunities for the educational sphere:

- Organization of the differential and individual training process;
- feedback link: self-control and correction of students;
- the use of computer and information technology such as animation, graphics, multiplications, sound in the lessons;
- to give students skills to master science, etc.

The basis of knowledge is practice. Information technology, on the other hand, has its advantage in this respect. The presence of the opportunity to shed light even in practical terms on the basis of technical means of learned theoretical knowledge ensures a more active participation of students in the educational process. The effective organization of information reception and appropriation, bilateral communication (between teacher and student, student and student) requires a high level of student activity. In the implementation of information and methodological support in the educational process, the main task of information and Communication Technologies is to ensure bilateral communication. Without feedback, it is impossible to teach without constant communication between the teacher and the student. Educational motives occupy a special place in the effective organization of this process.

ICT, in turn, is one of the most important motivational factors. Because, the concentration of information, the exhibitionism, that is, the possibility of presenting a wide variety of that that the presence of the image, the use of animations, the presentation of information corresponding to the age and physiological characteristics of the educated bring to the surface the interest in education in students and the internal driving forces (motive) to acquire knowledge. The content of the work carried out in this regard consists in teaching how to grow a motive, how to put it.

Informatization is a whole set of tools and conditions for the development of Information Processes, a process that involves the creation of an appropriate technical, base, organizational, economic, cultural and educational reforms, which provides ample opportunities for the technologization of Education.

Modern technologies that strengthen the capabilities of mankind in Information production also determine the quality of the intellectual potential of an informed society, and such processes ensure the regular development of the informatization industry.

Operating on the basis of the effective use of information provides acceptable ways to solve the following tasks:

- processing information about the source and the process that takes place in it;
- regularly carry out periodic information about the course of processes and carry out controls on their basis.

The use of tools of computational teaching techniques provides for the acquisition of knowledge that is reported to the student by the teacher and (or) ICT, and the organization of the educational person's activities related to the re-creation of the studied material, its application in similar (analogous) situations. Although the application of this method with the use of information and communication technologies makes it possible to seriously improve the quality of the organization of the educational process, but does not make it possible to radically change the educational process in relation to the use of a traditionally used scheme (without information and communication technologies). In this respect, the use of research techniques in problematic Ham is more self-justifying. The problematic method of teaching takes advantage of the possibilities of information and Communication Technologies regarding the organization of the educational process as the search for solutions to put some kind of problem and solve it. The main goal is to maximise the increase in cognitive activity of learners.

Based on the knowledge gained in the educational process, the solution of various categories of issues is envisaged, as well as the acquisition and analysis of a number of additional knowledge that will be necessary to solve the problem posed. In this case, special attention is paid to the acquisition of skills related to the collection, sorting, analysis and transmission of information.

Information and communication technologies, like all industries in our country, are rapidly developing, which puts new tasks before educators. Providing this network with mature qualified personnel is a requirement of the time, and the application of information technologies in the training requires the educator to know the following:

- learning and creativity from information as a process;
- information and creative processes in science and technology and culture;
- problems of development of society in information;
- information systems and knowledge-giving methods of artificial intelligence;
- technical means of information and telecommunications;
- to know and be able to apply an informative information system about educational materials;
- universal and problematic-technologies with an idea of the software tools for the implementation of remote information technologies;
- fundamentals of Information Modeling;
- automation system of training and control;
- use of global internet computer network;
- application of practical application packages in the educational process;
- having skills in the use of email in the learning process.
- development of the structure, content of the educational subject, which is intended to be written to the disk.
- develop a set of questions for independent work, mastering and strengthening.
- drawing up test questions, conducting tests and exams to test knowledge.

- list of resources for in-depth study of material, catalog of literature, development of topics of creative work.

- organizing teleconferences, organizing an active discussion, preparing an abstract, a list of topics for independent work.

- perform training exercises, control their sequence and analyze assessment forms.

- to make a proposal to analyze and improve the results of training.

- conducting control work.

It is worth noting that educational and educational electronic resources serve as a means of increasing the capabilities of educators, but it is natural that they cannot replace an educator.

In the joint activities of computers and people, the need for people is reflected. In this case, the educator who is the administrator of this process directs the goals of the educator on a certain basis. Joint activities and communication occur in conditions of social control.

This process manifests itself in a special way between the learner and the computer. In doing so, the teacher assigns part of his duties to the computer, but, retains the role of Administrator. Also defines the types of "feedback". That is, such as recording the results on the computer, conducting controls and, on this basis, controlling the knowledge of students.

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